
SPECIAL FEATURES OF THE ORGANIZATION OF EMPLOYMENT OF THE POPULATION IN ENSURING THE INNOVATIVE STABILITY OF THE ECONOMY

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Abstract

This article provides information on the special features of the organization of employment of the population in the process of sustainable economic changes, indicators of temporary employment in the case of member states of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development.

Key words

Sustainable economic development, human capital, employment indicators, labor market, Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, temporary employment.

In the conditions of stable economic development, it is important to modernize the labor market and increase its social efficiency. Formation of modern forms of labor is important in ensuring the employment of the population, in attracting qualified workers to the labor market. The reason is work - creativity, that is, creating material and spiritual blessings or restoring lost blessings. The work of a scientist, engineer, worker, farmer, artist, doctor and other creative persons is part of the same activity. Even if a person consciously performed unnecessary work for a specific purpose, such work is not considered labor.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev stated in his speech at the meeting at Nagoya University, "In the modern world, human capital, intellectual potential, innovative ideas, high technologies form the fundamental basis of rapid and stable development." According to statistics, more than 2 billion workers in the world (62% of the employed) are informally employed and therefore do not have labor rights and social protection.

Researchers distinguish several models of employment promotion policies in industrialized countries based on the interrelationship between economic growth, employment and labor productivity. In particular, researchers have identified five

types of employment and labor market regulation: the American model (USA), the Scandinavian model (Sweden, Finland, Denmark, Norway), the Anglo-Saxon model (Great Britain, Canada, Ireland), the continental or German model (Germany, Austria, Belgium, the Netherlands, Switzerland, partly France) and Japanese models. But some researchers group countries differently, for example, instead of dividing the American model into parts, they add it to the Anglo-Saxon model. Some researchers study countries by dividing them into three models (American, Scandinavian, European).⁶¹

The following main aspects are distinguished in the new system of labor organization and management in enterprises:

1. In enterprises, the hierarchical organizational structure characteristic of the old management system is being replaced by a flexible network management structure that provides for the transfer of authority and responsibility of enterprise management. As a result of these reforms, executive and management tasks will be combined, which will lead to a narrowing of the sphere of control of the management staff. As the control functions of the management are focused on the tasks of supporting the initiatives, the mutual cooperation between the related executives will increase.

2. Hired employees are involved in the production management process through flexible forms and methods of labor organization. Due to the activities of brigades with alternative and independent management, informal groups, and activities aimed at improving the quality of labor, employees become direct participants in the enterprise's activities.

3. Instead of the time-specific wage system in gross production, a flexible material system that provides for the payment of wages for labor according to the contribution of each employee or labor team to the enterprise's activity, as well as the establishment of additional rewards for skill improvement incentive system is being introduced. In this system, participation of employees in the share capital of the enterprise is supported.

4. A management culture is being formed to attract hired employees to the company's activities. The work team as a team realizes the unique aspects and individuality of each employee, the creative potential, mutual trust is formed among the team, and responsibility for the enterprise's activities is formed.

⁶¹ <https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/documents/ga4dhdaa2a9f352b0445bafbc79ca799dce4d.pdf>

5. In order to increase the efficiency of production, cooperation relations between the management of the enterprise, trade unions and employees will be strengthened.

One of the main areas of flexibility in developed countries is temporary employment, which includes various forms of employment. According to statistics, in 2022, the share of temporary employees in the structure of employment was 11,2% in the member states of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), and 14,2% in the countries of the European Community. This indicator is relatively low in the G7 countries.

It is noteworthy that this type of employment has different levels of development in different countries. For example, among the OECD countries, temporary employment is most common in Chile, Poland, Spain, and Portugal, where more than 20,0% of employees are temporarily employed.

Among these countries, the highest indicator is in Chile, where more than 28,7% of total employment is temporary employment. In the countries of Slovenia, Sweden, Finland, Italy and Denmark, this indicator is 13-20%. The lowest rate is in Japan, Great Britain, Latvia, Estonia and Australia - less than 7,0%.

Between 1985 and 2022, the share of temporary workers in the countries of the European Community doubled. In different countries of the European Community, this indicator changed differently, for example, in Portugal, Italy, France, Holland, Japan, and mainly in Spain, this indicator increased, while in Latvia, Germany, Greece, a decreasing trend was observed.

The results of the analysis of the experience of the OECD states indicate that, in the context of strict procedures for hiring and firing employees with long-term employment contracts, the high cost of firing permanent employees increases the interest of employers in using temporary employment. Strict control of permanent jobs in accordance with the legal norms and liberalized norms for temporary employment have led to an increase in the number of temporary workers in France and Spain.

In OECD countries, women are more often employed in temporary jobs than men. For example, in 2022, 16,9% of women and 12,8% of men had temporary employment contracts. In the countries of the European Community, this indicator is lower - 15,2% of women and 13,2% of men. Based on this indicator, a significant difference of 14% is noticeable in Belgium, Finland and Japan.

Availability of part-time employment varies dramatically by age.

More than 30% of 15-24-year-olds are temporarily employed in the OECD countries, and this indicator is more than 40% in the European Community

countries. This indicator is 4-5 times more than in older age groups. A clear example is Spain, where temporary employment among the above-mentioned age group is more than 60%, in Germany and Sweden, around 55-57%. The majority of temporary employees are employed in the service sector, primarily in personal and social services. A significant part of temporary employees in the field of material production is employed in agriculture and construction. The smallest part of temporary employees works in the mining and metallurgical industry and the processing industry. Distribution of employment by main sectors The difference in the distribution of temporary employment is less than that of part-time employment.

An important source of income from labor activity is income from self-employment of the population, the share of which in the structure of total income in January-March 2023 amounted to 28,2%. The same indicator in 2019 was 31,5%.⁶²

The growth rate of income in January-March 2023 reached 118,3%, which ensured an increase in the nominal income of the population by 5,4%. The highest self-employment income growth rate was recorded in 2021 at 119,1%.

The main share of the income received from self-employment fell on Tashkent (11,9%), Samarkand (11,4%) and Fergana (9,1%) regions. On the contrary, Syrdarya region (2,4%), Republic of Karakalpakstan (3,4%), Navoi region (4,8%) are regions with the smallest share of income from self-employment.⁶³

Share of regions in total income from self-employment
(for January-March 2023)

⁶² file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/14.Comprehensive%20income%20population.pdf

⁶³ file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/14.Comprehensive%20income%20population.pdf

In order to take the youth policy in Uzbekistan to a new level, to develop effective solutions to the problems in the field of youth, to form modern entrepreneurial skills in them and to ensure the employment of young men and women by creating new jobs, the country's youth state a program of additional measures for the further development of the policy was also adopted. This program includes, among other things, the following:

- ❖ allocation of grants for innovative, practical and promising projects of young people;

- ❖ allocating subsidies for drilling (digging) wells, purchasing irrigation equipment, installing light construction greenhouses, purchasing seeds and seedlings in order to support youth employment in the regions;

- ❖ to train young people to become qualified specialists in the relevant field in the future, including training for entrepreneurship, involving experts in the field who have achieved high results in our country;

- ❖ organization of business accelerators on the basis of higher education institutions in all regions in order to form entrepreneurial skills of graduates;

- ❖ organizing business trips to local production and service organizations in order to interest young people in entrepreneurship and business and to teach them the practical aspects of starting such activities;

- ❖ reimbursement of costs related to vocational training of young people, as well as costs of consulting services to provide practical assistance to young entrepreneurs in legal, accounting, marketing, branding, banking, insurance, labor and other areas;

- ❖ organizing trade fairs;

- ❖ conducting distance learning sessions and creating manuals aimed at teaching issues from starting a business to generating income⁶⁴.

Based on the above analysis, it is appropriate to implement the following tasks in order to ensure the employment of the population.

⁶⁴ <https://www.canada.ca/en/employment-social-development/corporate/youth-expert-panel/report-modern-strategies-youth-employment.html>

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